

Rural Survey on Organic Farming in India

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ABSTARCT

This study's primary goal is to promote organic farming because it is in high demand and does well for the environment or climate. As the ecosystem changes, the climate and atmosphere degrade day by day, wreaking havoc on not just the current generation but also the next. Ecology an interconnected system in which the disruption of the food chain or web will have a significant negative impact on the entire ecosystem. Organic farming is a significant alternative to synthetic/conventional agriculture since it increases ecosystem regeneration while also reducing pollution.

Keywords: Survey, Organic Farming, Ecology, Climate, Agriculture

Organic crops are grown in healthy, biologically active soils. Crops raised on organic farms mature more slowly and often yield less per acre than those raised in industrial agriculture. Furthermore, vegetables cultivated on organic farms are more likely to be nourished by soil that has higher concentrations of vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants. Organic

food is good in terms of health issues. Everyone is impacted by the numerous problems with the conventional food system, including illiteracy, water pollution, birth deformities, the misery of farm animals, and many more. The certified organic seal promotes giving people the things they require in today's society, like wholesome food, pure water, products created without pesticides, etc. In order to make their animals

grow bigger, quicker, and produce more milk than they would naturally, the majority of traditional farmers employ a range of poisons, drugs, growth hormones, and supplements. As a result, we consume more of these goods every day and use more antibiotics. All of these will see a decrease in consumption thanks to organic farming. The National Organic Program law prohibits almost all synthetic animal medications, thus healthy animals will ultimately produce healthy milk, meat, dairy products, eggs, etc. Create a healthy atmosphere at work and in the neighborhood. Farming is the second-riskiest job on the list of mining jobs. Numerous people who live or work near farms are at risk from harmful insecticides, caustic fertilizers, and other chemicals until the necessary protections are established.

Importance of Organic Agriculture:

A relevant and necessary alternative agricultural system is one that is environmentally benign, given the drawbacks of the widespread use of chemical farming methods in the second half of the 20th century. The farming methods used by our predecessors, which were refined and adopted over a long period of time, were less damaging to the environment. People began to think about various alternative farming

techniques based on environmental protection, which would improve human welfare in a variety of ways, such as through the production of clean and healthy foods, the development of an ecosystem that is favourable to the survival of all living and non-living things, and the use of fewer non-renewable energy sources. Numerous farming methods have been developed by both experts and everyday people. However, organic farming is regarded as the best of all due to its scientific methods and broad acceptance worldwide.

Organic Farming for Farmers:

Farmers use much fewer harmful chemicals when they switch to organic farming, protecting the health of their employees and rural neighbours.

The following are some reasons why farmers should switch to organic farming:

- 1) There is a limited supply of organic food compared to the demand
- 2) Costs of production are typically higher because more labour is required per unit of output
- 3) A greater variety of businesses makes it difficult to achieve economies of scale.

Increased costs are incurred for post-harvest handling of relatively small quantities of organic commodities because of the enforced separation of organic and conventional food, particularly for processing and shipping. Because there aren't as many organic items as possible available, marketing and the supply chain are less effective, and costs are greater.

As demand for organic food and products grows, technological developments and economies of scale should reduce the costs of growing, processing, transporting, and selling organic produce. Furthermore, it is stated that the cost of organic food includes a variety of factors that are not accounted for in the cost of conventional food, such as: Environmental enhancement and protection (and avoidance of future expenses to mitigate pollution). For instance, higher prices for organic cash crops compensate for lesser financial gains from the rotating intervals required to boost soil fertility.

Reducing the health concerns that inappropriate pesticide usage poses to farmers (and prevention of future medical costs). development of rural communities by adding additional farm jobs and making sure farmers get paid fairly and adequately.

Social & Political Factors:

Aiming to provide privileges in exchange for electoral advantages, political meddling in India's agriculture sector. Some of the tools frequently used to achieve political goals include government-controlled prices of inputs like chemical fertilizers, the dominance of public sector companies in the production of fertilizers, government support/floor prices for many agricultural products, the provision of inputs like power and water either for free or at a reduced rate, etc. Any campaign to support organic farming in India will face opposition from the parties who benefit from such methods in the traditional farming system. The political system in a democracy like India is prone to refrain from creating policies that have an influence on the interests of the voting blocs unless there are stronger opposition forces pushing for change. Due to a lack of other employment opportunities and other circumstances, the organized workforce, particularly in the public sector fertilizer, pesticide, and seed industries, is also likely to resist government measures to support organic farming on a large scale.

CONCLUSION

1. Developing appropriate and strong extension services.

2. Developing strong linkage between producer and consumer.

3. Reducing the cost of certification and easily approachable to farmer.

4. Making the organic inputs available to small holders like bio-fertilizer and bio-pesticide.

5. Enhancing linkages in the supply chain promoting research on organic agricultural research and development.

6. Conserving inherent soil nutritional quality and soil health, and biodiversity.

7. Developing the domestic market.

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